

ОЦЕНКА УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ РАЗНОВИДНОСТЕЙ ТВЕРДОЙ ПШЕНИЦЫ (*T. DURUM* DESF.) НА ОСНОВЕ ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПАРАМЕТРОВ

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ESTIMATION OF TOLERANCE OF DIFFERENT DURUM WHEAT (*T. DURUM* DESF.) GENOTYPES BASED ON PHYSIOLOGICAL PARAMETERS

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Аннотация

В лабораторных условиях изучено действие стрессовых факторов на физиологические процессы, особенно степень депрессии хлорофилла «а» и «б». Также было определено содержание хлорофилла а+б и их соотношение. С помощью этого диагностического метода определено засухо и солеустойчивость у 30 разновидностей твердой пшеницы. Установлено что, 6 образцов являются устойчивыми ко всем стресс факторам.

Abstract

The effect of stress factors on physiological processes, especially the degree of depression of chlorophyll "a" and "b" were studied under laboratory conditions. The contents of chlorophyll a+b and their ratio were also determined. Drought and salt tolerance of samples were determined in 30 durum wheat varieties. Six samples were selected and recorded as tolerant to stress factors.

Ключевые слова: пшеница, засуха, засоленность, хлорофилл, клейковина, стекловидность.

Keywords: wheat, drought, salinity, chlorophyll, gluten, vitrescence.

Introduction. The deterioration of the ecological situation and the depletion of genetic resources of plants makes us create a new quality, stress-resistant and adaptable to modern climatic conditions varieties. Especially, considering that arable lands are rapidly becoming drought resistant and exposed to salinization, there is a need for immediate action. Currently, 45 million hectares of 230 million hectares of irrigated land, approximately 20% of them have become salt-affected lands. Drought impact is observed in 26% of the arable areas compared to other stress factors.

Currently, the Genetic Resources Institute of the Ministry of Science and Education conducts extensive research works in connection with the collection and multiplication of wheat species and species diversity, and the problem of protection the biodiversity of the genetic fund. The biomorphological and economic features of nearly 1,000 collected wheat genotypes were investigated comprehensively. Their degree of resistance to biotic and abiotic stress factors is determined, the use of genotypes with beneficial

properties in breeding is recommended. Our research is part of the solution to this issue.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The studies were carried out on 30 samples of 14 durum wheat varieties (*T. durum* Desf.).

Leaf samples from the field experiment (second leaf from the top) were delivered to the laboratory and exposed to salt and drought stress to study the relationship between the salinity and drought stress tolerance and chlorophyll content of wheat genotypes. The leaves were cut out into small circles and divided into three variants. 5 circles from each variant of the experiment were placed into petri dishes. The samples were placed into water, 2% NaCl solution, 20 atm. pressurized sucrose solution and stored at 240° C. for a day. Then they were taken out of the solution, dried with filter paper, and transferred into a 10-ml test tube; after adding alcohol, it was boiled for several minutes (until the disks turned white).

After cooling, the volume of alcohol in the test tube was filled up to 10 ml and the amount of chlorophyll was measured on a spectrophotometer:

chlorophyll "a" at a wavelength of 665 nm and chlorophyll "b" at a wavelength of 649 nm. The ratio of the density of the pigment in the salt and drought-resistant versions to the water version was detected, and this ratio was taken as a measurement criterion for the selection of salt-resistant and drought-resistant forms. The samples with high results were considered to be tolerant [2].

They determined the physical parameters of the grains of the samples - the amount of gluten, sedimentation and quality, sediment sedimentation [3-6]. They studied the vitreousness, 1000 grains weight according to accepted methods (ДC-10842-64, 10840-64), the quantity and quality of gluten (ДC-9406-60), evaluated the gluten quality, stickiness values of dough (IDK-1 device). Sedimentation index was determined by acetic acid on the basis of macromethod [7-10].

Results and their discussion

The evaluation of the reaction to the change in physiological parameters of different varieties of wheat due to stress shows the sensitivity of these samples to salt and drought resistance and allows selection of resistant samples.

In fact the pigments are responsible for oxygen transfer in the photosynthesis process, oxidative and photosynthetic phosphorylation, in the general exchange of substances in the plant's organism. Chlorophylls (chlorophyll "b") play an important role in the plant's adaptation to adverse environmental factors. The decrease or increase in the ratio of chlorophyll "a" to "b" is seriously reflected in the physiological processes caused in the plant.

The results of studies on the determination of the chlorophyll content due to the effect of stress on the leaves of durum wheat are shown in table 1. The table shows chlorophyll "a", "b", the sum of "a" and "b", and the ratio of "a" to "b" in the leaves of wheat varieties subjected to drought and salt stress.

Plant photosynthesis indicators are exposed to large changes depending on the genetic characteristics of varieties and agroecological conditions.

According to the results, 6 drought-tolerant samples and 8 salt-tolerant samples were selected and indicated by (-) in Table 1.

Mutito-leucurum (17-K-1) in the table differed due to its high photochemical activity of chloroplasts among the selected varieties. In this sample, chlorophyll "a" was 2.71 μg in the control variant, 3.2 in the drought, and 3.99 μg in the salinity variant. The chlorophyll "b" indicators were 1.10 in the control, in the drought - 1.61, in the salt variant - 2.20 μg .

Based on the results, the percentage indicator of chlorophyll (a+b) content in this sample was 121 and 162 in the salt variant compared to the control, and this sample was selected as tolerant because of the high photochemical activity of the leaves.

The ratio of chlorophyll "a" to "b" in leaves increases their ability to absorb energy of certain wavelengths of the solar light when assessing the drought and salinity resistance of plants.

High ratio of chlorophyll "a" to "b" after drought and salt stress effect was found in 4 samples: *Obscurum* (17K-19); *mut. alexandrina* (13K-62); *Affine* (17K-15); *Albo obscurum* (17k-30); *Melanopus* (18K-54).

Table 1.

Indicators of drought and salinity tolerance caused changes in the leaf chlorophyll content of durum wheat (*T. durum* Desf.)

№ Catalogue	Sample name	Chlorophyll content (unit leaf area, in mcg)						Ca+Cb and Ca/Cb parameters: (in % according to control)			
		Control		Drought		Salinity		Drought		Salinity	
		a	b	a	b	a	b	a+b	a/b	a+b	a/b
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	St. Barakatli 95	8,95	2,95	9,30	2,80	6,04	3,27	101=	109=	78≡	60≡
17k-1	<i>Mutico leucurum</i>	2,71	1,10	3,02	1,61	3,99	2,20	121-	76≡	162-	73≡
17k-5	<i>Mutico Hordeiforme</i>	7,61	2,58	7,01	1,76	6,46	2,09	86≡	135-	84≡	105=
17 k-6	<i>Murciense</i>	7,3	0,57	1,73	0,53	2,18	0,87	98=	107-	132-	82≡
17 k-7	<i>Murciense</i>	1,73	0,69	1,80	0,84	2,75	1,36	170-	81≡	109=	85≡
17k-15	<i>Affine</i>	1,87	0,70	2,00	0,65	2,96	0,84	97=	115-	138-	132-
17k-18	<i>Mut Murciense</i>	1,78	0,68	2,09	0,84	2,75	1,12	119-	95=	157-	94≡
17k-19	<i>Obscurum</i>	7,04	2,78	8,53	2,58	8,59	2,30	113-	130-	111-	147-
18k-58	<i>Hordeiforme</i>	6,84	2,54	7,37	2,90	8,70	2,52	109=	94=	119-	128-
18k-59	<i>Melanopus</i>	7,99	3,21	7,38	2,85	8,44	3,09	91=	104-	103=	110-
18k-24	<i>Africanum</i>	7,51	2,74	1,86	1,09	2,58	0,84	131-	83≡	152-	150-
18k-33	<i>Mut.Lubicum</i>	7,09	2,08	7,64	2,16	8,23	2,40	106=	103=	116-	100=
17k-26	<i>Nilotium</i>	7,78	2,90	8,45	2,95	8,35	2,89	107=	107=	105=	107=
17k-26	<i>Obscurum</i>	1,22	0,46	1,57	0,48	6,13	1,76	122-	123-	116-	90≡
17k-30	<i>Albo obscurum</i>	1,65	0,66	4,71	1,40	2,50	0,65	91≡	136-	170-	153-
18k-26	<i>Albo obscurum</i>	6,01	1,75	6,69	1,92	6,56	1,76	110-	101=	107=	107=
18k-52	<i>Niloticum</i>	1,36	0,38	2,00	0,70	2,23	0,80	155-	174-	79≡	77≡
18k-53	<i>Murciense</i>	6,54	2,07	7,83	2,34	7,81	2,38	118-	118-	105=	104=
18k-54	<i>Melanopus</i>	4,52	1,79	5,28	1,60	7,21	2,10	109=	130-	147-	136-

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
18k-55	<i>Erythromelan</i>	5,95	2,33	6,18	2,45	6,37	2,46	104=	98≡	106=	101=
18k-57	<i>Apulicum</i>	6,07	2,37	7,53	1,90	7,21	2,60	111-	108=	116-	108=
18k-59	<i>Leucomelan</i>	5,49	2,22	6,16	2,05	7,02	2,17	106=	121-	119-	131-
18k-60	<i>Hordeiforme</i>	5,53	2,17	5,37	1,77	6,09	2,27	93≡	109-	116-	103=
18k-49	<i>Murciense</i>	7,65	2,54	7,77	2,28	7,94	3,60	98≡	113-	113-	73≡
18k-62	<i>Mut.Alexsadrinum</i>	1,51	0,74	2,23	0,80	2,93	0,86	134-	168-	136-	166-
18k-64	<i>Melanopus</i>	2,06	0,44	2,23	0,80	3,20	0,71	121-	58≡	156-	96=
18k-73	<i>Mut.apulicum</i>	1,92	0,51	2,30	0,99	2,93	0,86	135-	61≡	155-	90=
18k-96	<i>Hordeiforme</i>	3,09	1,23	2,87	1,12	4,14	1,31	92≡	126-	101=	125-
18k-97	<i>Hordeiforme</i>	2,46	0,78	3,30	1,39	3,92	0,99	144-	75≡	151-	126-
18k-99	<i>Leucurum</i>	1,36	0,38	1,86	0,77	2,64	0,58	151-	185-	67≡	127-

legend: - tolerant ; = moderatre tolerant; ≡ susceptible.

St. Barakatli - 95 and 21 durum wheat genotypes were collected and studied in 2021 at the Absheron Experimental Research Base. Physical parameters, qualitative and quantitative analyses of wheat gluten were carried out.

Any genetic marker that adequately describes the biodiversity of durum wheat varieties and, mainly, the genetic distance between varieties, should be chosen according to the different types of markers that can give different, sometimes even contradictory results.

Despite the fact that they are controlled by unrelated domains, this reflects the mosaic structure of the genome and suggests that the tools of evolution act somewhat independently.

As a result of the study, satisfactory results were obtained due to the vitescence and 1000 seed weight. According to the control variant, the highest percentage of vitescence was observed in 17k-6 *v. mursiense*

(100%) (Table № 2), and this result varied between 95-99% among 8 samples. The lowest vitescence was observed in 13k-53 *v. mursiense* (52%). 1000 grain weight in 9 samples was more than 50 g, the results varied between 50.8 - 59.2 g, 59.2 g was observed in the sample of *v. erythromelan*, the lowest indicator on 1000 grains weight was found in *v.coerulesens* samples.

This indicator was 48.8 g in the St.Barakatli-95. The results obtained are shown in Table 2. This year, only one sample (17k-6 *v. murciense*) had a gluten content of 40.0%. In the remaining 20 samples, this indicator ranged from 18.3% (18k-68 *st. muticoalexandrina*) to 35.7%, while this indicator was 28.0% in the st.Barakatli-95.

The quality of the gluten was lower depending on the weather conditions. The results of 21 samples are shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

Physical and quality features of durum wheat genotypes

№ Catalogue	Sample name	Physical features		The quantity and quality of gluten			
		Vitescence, %	100 grains weight, gr.	Stickiness, sm.	Amount, %	GDI c.g.	Dry gluten, %
	St. Barakatli-95	32	48.8	28.0	120	8	6.0
17k-1	<i>v.mutico-leucurum</i>	99	43.6	35.7	95	14	17.3
17k-6	<i>v. murciense</i>	100	47.2	40.0	95	10	19.5
18k-62	<i>v.aleksandrina</i>	95	44.8	35.5	100	8	14.2
18k-55	<i>v.erythromelan</i>	69	57.2	33.0	100	9	13.7
18k-24	<i>v.africanum</i>	74	54.4	20.0	120	18	9.4
	<i>v. coerulesens</i>	97	42.0	31.0	100	7	12.9
17k-26	<i>v.niloticum</i>	95	50.8	26.2	120	20	9.7
17k-19	<i>v.obscurum</i>	76	46.0	27.0	110	10	10.7
	<i>v. mutico-provinsale</i>	79	47.2	-	-	-	-
18k-58	<i>v.hordeiforme</i>	57	56.4	22.4	110	9	8.4
18k-53	<i>v.murciense</i>	52	53.2	28.4	110	9	9.9
	<i>v. leucomelan</i>	76	46.0	27.5	100	9	9.9
18k-60	<i>v.hordeiforme</i>	55	55.2	22.5	110	9	8.5
18k-62	<i>v.mutico-aleksandrina</i>	69	53.0	18.3	110	11	5.8
	<i>v.mutico-lybicum</i>	99	39.6	-	-	-	-
	<i>v. erythromelan</i>	95	56.0	33.0	100	8	12.0
17k-5	<i>v.mutico-hordeiforme</i>	98	49.2	19.0	110	8	6.4
18k-52	<i>v.niloticum</i>	78	48.0	25.6	110	7	8.3
	<i>v. erythromelan</i>	56	59.2	20.7	120	12	8.0

Table 3.

Durum wheat genotypes selected for their high performance

№ Catalogue	Sample name	Physical features		The quantity and quality of gluten			
		Vitrescence, %	1000 grains weight, gr.	Stickiness, cm	Amount, %	GDI c.g.	Dry gluten, %
17k-1	v.mutico-leucurum	99	43.6	14	35.7	95	17,3
17k-6	v. murciense	100	47.2	10	40	95	19,5
18k-62	v.aleksandrina	95	44.8	8	35.5	100	14,2
18k-55	v.erythromelan	69	57.2	9	33	100	13,7
17k-7	v. coerulesens	97	42.0	7	31.0	100	12,9
18k-52	v. erythromelan	95	56.0	8	33.0	100	12,0
St.Barakatli-95		32	48.8	8	28.0	100	10,0

According to the the studies of this year, 6 genotypes with high rates were selected and compared with the indicators of the st.Barakatli-95 variety, and listed in Table 3.

Among the studied specimens, satisfactory quality features were observed in *v. murciense*, *v. mutico-leucurum*, *v. mutico. alexandrina*, *v. erythromelan* and

v. Coerulescens, in spite of of adverse weather conditions. These samples can be used as an initial material for breeding as a stable hybrid form.

The high results of the vitreousness and dry gluten are shown in a diagram (Fig. 1). As can be seen from the figure, these features are close to each other.

Fig. 1.

Results

1. 100% vitrescence was observed only in one sample (*v. murciense*), and this result ranged within 95-99% among eight samples. 1000 grains weight was higher than 50 grams in nine samples, the results varied between 50.8 - 59.2 gr, so the highest result was observed in *v.erythromelan* (59.2 g).

2. Satisfactory quality features were observed in *v. murciense*, *v. mutico-leucurum*, *v. mutico. alexandrina*, *v. erythromelan* and *v. Coerulescens*, in spite of adverse weather conditions. The results of vitreousness and dry gluten were close to each other. These samples can be used as an initial material for breeding as a stable hybrid form.

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